

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Experimental validation of a multi-solver heat transfer simulation methodology including occupant thermo-physiology

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404473

Julien Joris¹, Sidali Mokdad¹, Roch El Khoury^{1*}, Gabriel Crehan²

¹Institut VEDECOM, 77 rue des Chantiers, 78000 Versailles, France

²Groupe PSA- Centre Technique de Vélizy A, Route de Gisy, 78140 Vélizy-Villacoublay, France

*Corresponding author: roch.elkhoury@vedecom.fr

Introduction

Operating the HVAC system (Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning), which is mandatory for road safety as well as maintaining good cabin air quality and passenger thermal comfort, dominates all auxiliaries' energy consumption in electric vehicles (EVs). This can go as far as halving the range of an EV under certain operating conditions. In order to address the passenger thermal comfort needs in car cabins, especially EVs, a fully coupled transient simulation methodology covering conduction, solar and infrared radiation, convection, fluid and species transport along with occupant thermo-physiology is proposed. An experimental validation of the numerical simulation predictions is performed using human tests in a controlled thermal environment.

Experimental environment and human tests

A thermal test bench that represents a B-segment car cabin was used for the experiments. The internal walls of the test cell are covered with 42 independent flat stainless steel heat exchangers reproducing the car cabin geometry. Their temperatures can be precisely controlled from 5 to 45°C using an independent water-glycol circulation circuit. An air handling unit provides control over the mass flow rate, temperature, and humidity of the air that is injected into the cabin. Several temperature probes monitor surface, air as well as interface contact temperatures throughout the tests. Other environmental parameters like the black globe temperature, air humidity, and airflow velocities are also measured around the subjects. Experimental results of 10 human testers under transient conditions were used to validate the coupled simulation approach. All human subjects were provided with identical thermally characterized clothes for the experiments. They were also fitted with wireless skin temperature and humidity sensors at 36 different location of their bodies, as shown in the fig.1. Each tester went through the following exposure:

1. 30 minutes of sedentary preconditioning at 25°C in a separate room
2. 30 minutes in the driver seat inside the test bench at 45°C (air and surface temperatures)
3. 60 minutes during which the air and surface temperatures transition to 25 °C

Throughout the test, air flow and humidity from the air handling unit were fixed at 250m³/h and 50 % respectively. All temperature sensors were calibrated using a standard Pt100 thermometer with an accuracy of 0.2°C.

Fig.1: Test bench setup and locations of the sensors on the human subjects

Transient multi-physical simulation methodology

The proposed multi-physical simulation methodology provides the capabilities to model radiative heat transfer, conduction and convection, airflow and fluid dynamics in the cabin, including turbulence and

specifies transport as well as occupant thermo-physiology. It relies on existing specialized and widely validated CFD and Finite Element solvers, with the development effort being focused on their coupling and optimal use to provide multi-physical capabilities mandatory to address cabin occupant thermal comfort and energy management.

On the one hand, 3D transient heat transfer and thermo-physiology simulation is performed in a specialized Finite Element solver that also provides an implementation of the Fiala thermo-physiological model. On the other hand, a Finite Volume CFD solver is used for the simulation of complex 3D fluid flows. Solver coupling is achieved by exchanging thermal boundary conditions at the coupled interfaces at each simulation time step, allowing the solvers to yield a prediction of skin and surface temperatures that accounts for all detailed coupled heat transfer phenomena. The coupled simulation is performed using measured input parameters from the experiments i.e. temperature of the walls, air temperature, and humidity profiles.

Results and discussions

Skin temperature profiles predicted using the proposed coupled multi-solver methodology are compared to the experimental measurements performed on the 10 human subjects and to the results of a standalone Finite Element thermal simulation (without CFD coupling).

Although the experimental setup is highly repeatable and reproducible, the skin temperatures profile of the human subjects may differ by over 3°C at a given time during the exposure. We note that thermo-neutrality of the different subjects results in a different skin temperature distribution, and thus a different initial temperature. Nevertheless, the coupled standard Fiala thermo-physiology model provides a good prediction for the average response of the sample. It is also interesting to note that the CFD coupling has a non-negligible impact on the skin temperature profile predictions when compared to the standalone Finite Element thermal simulation.

Fig.2 Mean skin temperature profiles: standalone v/s coupled simulation v/s experiment

Fig.3 Left arm skin temperature profiles: standalone v/s coupled simulation v/s experiment

Conclusions

A coupled multi-solver simulation approach covering radiation, conduction, convection, fluid flow and human thermo-physiology was presented and applied to model the thermal exposure of 10 different human subjects in a controlled thermal test bench. Simulation results were in good agreement with skin temperature measurements, performed on different body elements of the human subjects.

The skin temperature measurements followed the same average trend, for the same thermal exposure, with as much as 3°C difference between different testers especially at thermo-neutrality. Coupling the thermal simulation with CFD flow modeling considerably enhanced the accuracy of the results and proved essential for tight spaces like car cabins, where air flows are highly heterogeneous. Further cold conditions will be tested and validated using the same simulation methodology. Finally, the personalization of the thermo-physiological model may prove quite promising in order to account for inter-personal thermal response differences, helping to reproduce the measurement deviation between the different test subjects.